

Birth year	Names	First paper	PhD ступінь	Retired	Sex	Characteristics	Life years
1830	Johannes Vahlen	1852	1852	1911		German classical philologist	1830-1911
1830	Herbert Coleridge	1857		1861		British English philologist, technically the first editor of what ultimately became the Oxford English Dictionary	1830-1861
1830	Clémence Royer	1859		1887 w		French self-taught scholar who lectured and wrote on economics, philosophy, science and feminism	1830-1902
1830	Matthias Lexer	1860	1860	1892		German lexicographer, author of the principal dictionary of the Middle High German language	1830-1892
1830	Antonio Annetto Caruana	1862		1896		Maltese archaeologist and author	1830-1905
1831	Basil Lanneau Gildersleeve	1853	1853	1915		American classical scholar	1831-1924
1831	Willard Fiske	1859		1890		American librarian and scholar	1831-1904
1831	Salomon Lefmann	1864	1864	1901		German Jewish philologist	1831-1912
1831	Henry Bradshaw	1866		1886		British scholar and librarian	1831-1886
1832	Heinrich Julius Holtzmann	1858	1858	1910		German Protestant theologian	1832-1910
1832	John Camden Hotten	1859		1873		British English bibliophile and publisher (clandestine publishing of numerous erotic and pornographic titles)	1832-1873
1832	Edward Burnett Tylor	1861	1871	1909		British English anthropologist, the founder of cultural anthropology	1832-1917
1832	Georges Perrot	1862		1914		French archaeologist	1832-1914
1832	Anne Walbank Buckland	1872		1898 w		British anthropologist, ethnologist, and travel writer	1832-1899
1832	Ferdinand Kittel	1894		1903		German priest and indologist with the Basel Mission in south India and worked in Mangalore, Madikeri and Dharwad in Karnataka	1832-1903
1833	Sophus Bugge	1857	1857	1907		Norwegian philologist and linguist	1833-1907
1833	Georg Gerland	1859	1859	1919		German anthropologist and geophysicist	1833-1919
1833	August Fick	1868		1913		German philologist	1833-1916
1833	Peter Olrog Schjøtt	1880		1918		Norwegian philologist and politician	1833-1926
1834	Justus Hermann Lipsius	1856	1856	1914		German classical philologist	1834-1920
1834	Charlton Thomas Lewis	1861	1877	1899		American lawyer, author and lexicographer, who is particularly remembered as a compiler of several Latin–English dictionaries	1834-1904
1834	Ernst von Herzog	1862	1862	1911		German classical philologist and archaeologist, who as an expert in the field of Roman epigraphy	1834-1911

1834 Kuzman Shapkarev	1866	1909	Bulgarian folklorist, ethnographer and scientist	1834-1909
1834 Lucy Lloyd	1876	1889 w	British creator, along with Wilhelm Bleek, of the 19th-century archive of !Xam and !Kung texts	1834-1914
1834 William Morfill	1883	1909	British Professor of Russian and the other Slavonic languages	1834-1909